

Literature review for the Amazonia ILK case study

Final set of references

1. ACAIPI - Asociación de Capitanes y Autoridades Tradicionales Indígenas del Río Pirá Paraná, Fundación GAIA Amazonas, Fundación Rainforest. (2017). Diagnóstico del Gobierno Propio Indígena ACAIPI. Bogotá.
2. Acuña, R.Y. (2019). Palma de cumare se aprovecharía de manera sustentable. Available on: <https://agenciadenoticias.unal.edu.co/detalle/article/palma-de-cumare-se-aprovecharia-de-manera-sustentable.html> Access date: 17 May 2021
3. Afelt, Aneta, Roger Frutos, and Christian Devaux. 2018. 'Bats, Coronaviruses, and Deforestation: Toward the Emergence of Novel Infectious Diseases?' *Frontiers in Microbiology* 9 (April): 702. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2018.00702>.
4. Alejo, E.C. (2011). Impacto del uso sobre la estructura poblacional de dos especies de palmas. Alternativas participativas de manejo en la comunidad Ticuna de San Martín de Amacayacu. Tesis para optar al título de Biología, Universidad de los Andes.
5. André, R. 2020. 'Teaching Climate Leadership: Promoting Integrative Learning in Courses on Strong Sustainability'. *Journal of Management Education* 44 (6): 766–93. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1052562920941547>.
6. Bakalis, S., ValDRAMIDIS, V., and ARGYROPOULOS, D. 2020. 'Perspectives from CO+RE: How COVID-19 Changed Our Food Systems and Food Security Paradigms'. *Current Research in Food Science* 3: 166–72.
7. Balée, W. & C. Erickson 2006. Time, Complexity, and Historical Ecology. In *Time and Complexity in Historical Ecology: Studies in the Neotropical Lowlands*, edited by W. Balée & C.L. Erickson, p. 1-17. New York: Columbia University Press.
8. Balée, W. 1989. The Culture of Amazonian Forests. In *Resource Management in Amazonia: Indigenous and Folk Strategies*. *Advances in Economic Botany*, edited by D. Posey and W. Balée, p. 1-21. New York: New York Botanical Garden.
9. Balslev H., Kahn F., Millan B., Svenning J-C. et al. (2011). Species diversity and growth forms in tropical American palm communities. *The Botanical Review*, 77, 381–425.
10. Barnaud, C., Van Paassen, A. (2013). Equity, Power Games, and Legitimacy Dilemmas of Participatory Natural Resource Management. *Ecology and Society*, 18, 21. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5751/ES-05459-180221>
11. Belaunde, L. 2005. *El Recuerdo de Luna: Género, sangre y memoria entre los pueblos amazónicos*. Lima: Fondo Editorial de la Facultad de Ciencias Sociales Unidad de Post Grado de Ciencias Sociales.
12. Bertely Busque, M., María Elena Martínez Tor, and Rubén Muñoz Martínez. 2015. 'Autonomía, Territorio y Educación Intercultural. Actores Locales y Experiencias Comunitarias Latinoamericanas'. *Desacatos* 48: 6–11.
13. Blackman, Allen, and Peter Veit. 2018. 'Titled Amazon Indigenous Communities Cut Forest Carbon Emissions'. *Ecological Economics* 153 (November): 56–67.

14. Bocko, P. 2016. 'Synergy between Problem-Based Learning and Educating for Sustainability: A Review of the Literature'. In *Building for a Sustainable Future in Our Schools: Brick by Brick*, 107–31. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-12403-2_8.
15. Bonilla-Aldana, D. Katterine, Yeimer Holguin-Rivera, Soffia Perez-Vargas, Adrian E. Trejos-Mendoza, Graciela J. Balbin-Ramon, Kuldeep Dhama, Paola Barato, Charlene Lujan-Vega, and Alfonso J. Rodriguez-Morales. 2020. 'Importance of the One Health Approach to Study the SARS-CoV-2 in Latin America'. *One Health* 10: 100147.
16. Bugallo-Rodríguez, A., and P. Vega-Marcote. 2020. 'Circular Economy, Sustainability and Teacher Training in a Higher Education Institution'. *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSHE-02-2020-0049>.
17. Castaño, N., Cárdenas López, D., Rodríguez, E.O., (Ed.) (2007). *Ecología, aprovechamiento y manejo sostenible de nueve especies de plantas del departamento del Amazonas, generadoras de productos maderables y no maderables*. Instituto Amazónico de Investigaciones Científicas - Sinchi, Corporación para el Desarrollo Sostenible del Sur de la Amazonia - Corpoamazonia, Ministerio de Ambiente, Vivienda y Desarrollo Territorial. Bogotá: Editorial Scripto.
18. Celentano, Danielle, Guillaume X. Rousseau, Francisca Helena Muniz, István van Deursen Varga, Carlos Martinez, Marcelo Sampaio Carneiro, Magda V. C. Miranda, et al. 2017. 'Towards Zero Deforestation and Forest Restoration in the Amazon Region of Maranhão State, Brazil'. *Land Use Policy* 68 (November): 692–98.
19. Clement, C. 2006. Fruit Trees and the Transition to Food Production in Amazonia. En *Time and Complexity in Historical Ecology: Studies in the Neotropical Lowlands*, edited by W. Balée y C.L. Erickson, p. 165-185. New York: Columbia University Press.
20. Coronel M. y Solórzano J. (2017). *Comunidades locales y pueblos indígenas. Su rol en la conservación, mantenimiento y creación de áreas protegidas*. Iniciativa Visión Amazónica. REDPARQUES, WWF, FAO, UICN, ONU Medio Ambiente. XV +192pp
21. Coshikox - Consejo Shipibo Konibo Xetebo. 2020. *Conocimientos para curar: Experiencia del pueblo Shipibo Konibo! Organización Indígena del pueblo Shipibo/Konibo/Xetebo, Amazonía Peruana*. Presentación.
22. Cruz-García, G.S., Vanegas, M., Torres-Vitolas, C., Harvey, C.A. et al. (2019). He says, she says: Ecosystem services and gender among indigenous communities in the Colombian Amazon. *Ecosystem Services*, 37, 100921. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2019.100921>
23. Dasgupta Review (2020). *The Dasgupta Review – Independent Review on the Economics of Biodiversity Interim Report*. Available at: www.gov.uk/official-documents.
24. De Berenguer et al. 2020. Amazonian fires. Three animations available on: https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL_5Mw2w0vv1hSXVw8QHb2XLK4izDVlnz8
25. De Urzedo, D. & Fisher, R. 2018. How Brazil can beat the odds and restore a huge swathe of the Amazon. <https://theconversation.com/how-brazil-can-beat-the-odds-and-restore-a-huge-swathe-of-the-amazon-102116>
26. Denevan, W. 1992. The Pristine Myth: The Landscape of the Americas in 1492. *Annals of the Association of American Geographers* 82(3): 369-385.
27. Descola, P. 1986. *La nature domestique: Symbolisme et praxis dans l'ecologie des Achuar*. Paris: Editions de la Maison des sciences de l'homme.

28. Díaz, S., Demissew, S., Carabias, J., Joly, C., et al. (2015). The IPBES Conceptual 1845 Framework - Connecting nature and people. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 14, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2014.11.002>
29. El-Adaway, I., and D. Truax. 2012. 'Problem-Based-Learning and Learning-through-Service for Sustainability Education'. In , 2111–19. <https://doi.org/10.1061/9780784412329.212>.
30. Ellwanger, J.H., B. Kulmann-Leal, V.L. Kaminski, J.M. Valverde-Villegas, A.B.G. DA VEIGA, F.R. Spilki, P.M. Fearnside, et al. 2020. 'Beyond Diversity Loss and Climate Change: Impacts of Amazon Deforestation on Infectious Diseases and Public Health'. *Anais Da Academia Brasileira de Ciencias* 92 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1590/0001-3765202020191375>.
31. Erazo Acosta, Eduardo. 2020. 'Alli Kawsay: Epistemology and Political Practice in the Territories, a Possibility from the Andean Pluriverse for Ecological Justice and the Care of Mother Nature'. *The Palgrave Handbook of Climate Resilient Societies*, 1–17.
32. Erickson, C. 2010. The Transformation of Environment into Landscape: The Historical Ecology of Monumental Earthwork Construction in the Bolivian Amazon. *Diversity* 2: 618-652.
33. Ernst, J., and F. Burcak. 2019. 'Young Children's Contributions to Sustainability: The Influence of Nature Play on Curiosity, Executive Function Skills, Creative Thinking, and Resilience'. *Sustainability (Switzerland)* 11 (15). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11154212>.
34. Evans, Kristen, Laura Murphy, and Wil de Jong. 2014. 'Global versus Local Narratives of REDD: A Case Study from Peru's Amazon'. *Environmental Science & Policy, Climate change and deforestation: the evolution of an intersecting policy domain*, 35 (January): 98–108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2012.12.013>.
35. Everard, M., Johnston, P., Santillo, D., and Staddon, C. 2020. 'The Role of Ecosystems in Mitigation and Management of Covid-19 and Other Zoonoses'. *Environmental Science and Policy* 111: 7–17.
36. Fals-Borda, O. (1987). The application of participatory action-research in Latin America. *Int Sociol*, 2, 329-47.
37. Fals-Borda, O. (2001). Participatory (action) research in social theory: Origins and challenges. In P. Reason & H. Bradbury (Eds.), *Handbook of action research: Concise paperback edition* (pp. 27–37) . Thousand Oaks: Sage.
38. Fals-Borda, O., Rahman, M. A. (1991). *Action and knowledge: breaking the monopoly with participatory action research*. Intermediate Technology Publications, Apex Press, London, UK.
39. FAO. 2016. 'El Estado de Los Bosques Del Mundo 2016. Los Bosques y La Agricultura: Desafíos y Oportunidades En Relación Con El Uso de La Tierra.'
40. Fausto, C. & Neves, E. 2018 *Timeless Gardens: Deep Indigenous History and the Making of Biodiversity in the Amazon*. México: UNESCO, 35 p.
41. Fenichel, E.P., Abbott, J.K. (2014). Natural Capital: From Metaphor to Measurement. *Journal of the Association of Environmental and Resource Economists*, 1, 1-27. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1086/676034>
42. Ferguson, T. 2020. 'Environmental and Sustainability Education in the Caribbean: Crucial Issues, Critical Imperatives'. *Environmental Education Research* 26 (6): 763–71. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2020.1754342>.
43. FILAC – Fondo para el Desarrollo de los Pueblos Indígenas de América Latina y el Caribe. 2020. *Indigenous Peoples and COVID -19 - Beyond the Emergency*. Webinar, International Funders for Indigenous Peoples - IFIP June 2020.

44. Fung, D. 2018. 'Re-Thinking the Higher Education Curriculum: Challenges, Possibilities, and Dreams'. In *Places of Engagement. Reflections on Higher Education in 2040 - A Global Approach*, 82–87. Amsterdam University Press.
45. Gallemore, Caleb, and Kristjan Jespersen. 2016. 'Transnational Markets for Sustainable Development Governance: The Case of REDD+'. *World Development* 86 (October): 79–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2016.06.009>.
46. Garcés-Ruiz, M., Senés-Guerrero, C., Declerck, S., Cranenbrouck, S. (2018). Community composition of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi associated with native plants growing in a petroleum-polluted soil of the Amazon region of Ecuador. *Microbiology Open*, 8:e703. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mbo3.703>
47. Garí, J. (2001). Biodiversity and Indigenous Agroecology in Amazonia: The Indigenous Peoples of Pastaza. *Etnoecológica* 5, 21-37.
48. GEO Amazonia (2009). *Environment Outlook in Amazonia*. United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), Amazon Cooperation Treaty Organization (ACTO). Report, <http://www.unep.org/resources/report/environment-outlook-amazonia-geo-amazonia>
49. Goldammer, J. 1992. Tropical Forests in Transition: Ecology of Natural and Anthropogenic Disturbance Processes - An Introduction. In *Tropical Forests in Transition*, edited by J. Goldammer, p. 1-16. Switzerland: Birkhäuser Verlag Basel.
50. Goldel, B., Kissling, W.D., Svenning, J.C. (2015). Geographical variation and environmental correlates of functional trait distributions in palms (Arecaceae) across the New World. *Botanical Journal of the Linnean Society*, 2015, 179, 602–617.
51. Griffin; J. 2017. Brazilian supreme court upholds land rights of indigenous people. <https://www.theguardian.com/global-development/2017/aug/17/brazilian-supreme-court-upholds-land-rights-indigenous-people-mato-grosso-do-sul>
52. Gustavsson, C. 2020. 'Existential Configurations: A Way to Conceptualise People's Meaning-Making'. *British Journal of Religious Education* 42 (1): 25–35. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01416200.2018.1556598>.
53. Hallowell, I. 1960. Ojibwa ontology, behavior, and world view. In *Culture in History*, edited by S. Diamond. New York: Columbia University Press. Pp. 141-179.
54. Hanazaki, N., Zank, S., Fonseca-Kruel, V.S., Belloni-Schmidt, I. (2018). Indigenous and Traditional Knowledge, Sustainable Harvest, and the Long Road Ahead to Reach the 2020 Global Strategy for Plant Conservation Objectives. *Rodriguésia*, 69, 1587–1601. <https://doi.org/10.1590/2175-7860201869409>.
55. Hansen, M.C., Potapov, P.V., Moore, R., Hancher, M., et al. (2013). High-resolution global maps of 21st-century forest cover change. *Science*, 342, 850–853.
56. Hecht, S., Rajão, R. (2020). From "Green Hell" to "Amazonia Legal": Land Use Models and the Re-Imagination of the Rainforest as a New Development Frontier. *Land Use Policy*, 96, 103871. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2019.02.030>.
57. Heckenberger, M.J., A. Kuikuro, U.T. Kuikuro, J.C. Russell, M. Schmidt, C. Fausto and B. Franchetto. 2003. Amazonia 1492: Pristine forest or cultural parkland? *Science* 301: 1710-1713.
58. Hermann, R.R., M.B. Bossle, and M. Amaral. 2020. 'Lenses on the Post-Oil Economy: Integrating Entrepreneurship into Sustainability Education through Problem-Based Learning'. *Educational Action Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09650792.2020.1823239>.

59. Ing, D. 2011. 'Systems Thinking Courses in the Master's Programme on Creative Sustainability at Aalto University: Reflections on Design and Delivery of the 2010-2011 Sessions'. In , 551–76.
60. IPES – International Panel of Experts on Sustainable Food Systems. 2020. COVID-19 and the crisis in food systems: Symptoms, causes, and potential solutions Communiqué by IPES-Food, April 2020.
61. Irvine, D. 1987. Resource Management by the Runa Indians of the Ecuadorian Amazon. PhD Dissertation Stanford University, California, 306 pp.
62. Izquierdo Barrera, Martha Lucía. 2018. 'Educación En Contextos Multiculturales: Experiencia Etnoeducativa e Intercultural Con Población Indígena Del Resguardo Embera Chamí - Mistrató, Risaralda -- Colombia'. Education in Multicultural Contexts: Ethnoeducational and Intercultural Experience with an Indigenous Population from the Resguardo Embera Chami (Mistrato, Risaralda, Colombia)., no. 29 (July): 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.14482/zp.29.0002>.
63. Kehoe, L., Reis, T., Virah-Sawmy, M., Balmford, A., Kuemmerle, T. and 604 Signatories. (2019). Make EU Trade with Brazil Sustainable. Science, 364, 341–341. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaw8276>.
64. Kengen, S. (2019). Forestry in Brazil: A brief history, 99.
65. Kēpa, Mere, and Linitā Manu'atu. 2006. 'Indigenous Māori and Tongan Perspectives on the Role of Tongan Language and Culture in the Community and in the University in Aotearoa-New Zealand'. American Indian Quarterly 30 (1/2): 11–27.
66. Kimmerer, R. 2017 The Covenant of Reciprocity. In John Hart (ed). The Wiley Blackwell Companion to Religion and Ecology. First Edition. John Wiley & Sons Ltd. Pp. 368-381.
67. Kissling, W.D., Balslev, H., Baker, W.J., Dransfeld, J. et al (2019). PalmTraits 1.0, a species-level functional trait database of palms worldwide. Scientific data, 6:178. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-019-0189-0>
68. Langstroth, R. 1996. Forest islands in an Amazonian savanna of Northeastern Bolivia. Ph.D. Dissertation, Madison: University of Wisconsin, Department of Geography.
69. Lehmann J. 2009 Terra Preta Nova – Where to from Here?. In: Woods W.I., Teixeira W.G., Lehmann J., Steiner C., Winkler Prins A., Rebellato L. (eds) Amazonian Dark Earths: Wim Sombroek's Vision. Springer, Dordrecht. Pp. 473-486.
70. Levis C, Flores BM, Moreira PA, Luize BG, Alves RP, Franco-Moraes J, Lins J, Konings E, Peña-Claros M, Bongers F, Costa FRC and Clement CR 2018 How People Domesticated Amazonian Forests. Front. Ecol. Evol. 5:171. doi: 10.3389/fevo.2017.00171
71. Lima, Mendelson, Carlos Antonio da Silva Junior, Lisa Rausch, Holly K. Gibbs, and Jerry Adriani Johann. 2019. 'Demystifying Sustainable Soy in Brazil'. Land Use Policy 82 (March): 349–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2018.12.016>.
72. Linares, O. 1976. Garden hunting in the American Tropic. Human Ecology 4(4):331-350.
73. Local Biodiversity Outlooks 2. 2020. The contributions of indigenous peoples and local communities to the implementation of the Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011–2020 and to renewing nature and cultures. A complement to the fifth edition of the Global Biodiversity Outlook. Available at: www.localbiodiversityoutlooks.net
74. Lovejoy, T. E., Nobre, C. (2018). Amazon Tipping Point. Science Advances, 4, eaat2340. DOI: 10.1126/sciadv.aat2340

75. Maisonnave, F. 2019. Brazil's first indigenous congresswoman defends her people's rights from Bolsonaro <https://www.climatechangenews.com/2019/02/19/brazils-first-indigenous-congresswoman-defends-peoples-rights-bolsonaro/>
76. Maturana, R., Dávila, X., Ramírez, S. (2016). Cultural-Biology: Systemic Consequences of Our Evolutionary Natural Drift as Molecular Autopoietic Systems. *Foundations of Science*, 21, 631–678. DOI 10.1007/s10699-015-9431-1
77. McDougall, C. and Banjade, M.R. (2015). Social capital, conflict, and adaptive collaborative governance: exploring the dialectic. *Ecology and Society* 20, 44. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5751/ES-07071-200144>
78. McGibbon, C., and J.-P. Van Belle. 2015. 'Integrating Environmental Sustainability Issues into the Curriculum through Problem-Based and Project-Based Learning: A Case Study at the University of Cape Town'. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability* 16: 81–88. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2015.07.013>.
79. Ministerio de Educación Nacional. 2014. *Relatos del Pueblo Sikuani, Amazonia Colombiana*. 8. Bogotá: Ministerio de Educación Nacional.
80. Minkler, M. (2000). Using Participatory Action Research to Build Healthy Communities. *Public Health Reports*, 115, 191-197. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/4598511>
81. Mondragón, C. 2007 *Encarnando a los ancestros en la Melanesia: La innovación como mecanismo de continuidad en el norte de Vanuatu*. Cuadernos de trabajo 14. El Colegio de México, A.C. Centro de Estudios de Asia y África.
82. Moreno, F. (2006). Manejo de la palma chambira en el clan achote de la etnia Nonuya, comunidad de Peña Roja, medio río Caquetá, Amazonas. *Revista Semillas*, Edición 26/27. Available on: Manejo de la palma chambira. En el clan achote de la etnia nonuya, comunidad de Peña Roja, medio río Caquetá, Amazonas - Semill (semillas.org.co)
83. Mouchrek, N. 2018. 'Engaging College Students in the Transition to Sustainability Through Design-Based Approaches'. *Consilience*, no. 20: 88–103.
84. Muñoz-Rodríguez, J.M., F. Sánchez-Carracedo, A. Barrón-Ruiz, and S. Serrate-González. 2020. 'Are We Training in Sustainability in Higher Education? Case Study: Education Degrees at the University of Salamanca'. *Sustainability (Switzerland)* 12 (11). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12114421>.
85. Nación Sápara del Ecuador. 2016. 'Cuentos Sáparas.Pdf'. Google Docs. 2016. https://drive.google.com/file/d/1MtHa6A2JrUTuvV_MfPBg9fCtkE_ZDGIL/view?usp=drive_web&usp=embed_facebook.
86. Nejedeka Jifichú, Célimo Ramón. 2019. *Cultivando La Ciencia Del Árbol de La Salud. Conocimiento Tradicional Para El Buen Vivir*. Pontificia Universidad Javeriana. Bogotá.
87. Nepstad, D. et al. 2006. Inhibition of Amazon deforestation and fire by parks and indigenous lands. *Conservation Biology* 20, 65–73.
88. Nobre, Carlos Afonso, and Laura De Simone Borma. 2009. "'Tipping Points" for the Amazon Forest'. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability* 1 (1): 28–36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2009.07.003>.
89. Nolte, C., de Waroux, Y.P., Munger, J., Reis, T.N.P., Lambin, E.F. (2017). Conditions Influencing the Adoption of Effective Anti-Deforestation Policies in South America's Commodity Frontiers. *Global Environmental Change*, 43, 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2017.01.001>.

90. O’Riordan, T., G. Jacobs, J. Ramanathan, and O. Bina. 2020. ‘Investigating the Future Role of Higher Education in Creating Sustainability Transitions’. *Environment* 62 (4): 4–15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00139157.2020.1764278>.
91. Oliveira, P.J.C., Gregory, A., David, K. et al. (2007). Land-use allocation protects the Peruvian Amazon. *Science*, 317, 1233–1236
92. Osborne, Tracey. 2015. ‘Tradeoffs in Carbon Commodification: A Political Ecology of Common Property Forest Governance’. *Geoforum* 67 (December): 64–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2015.10.007>.
93. Ovando, P., Brouer, R. (2019). A review of economic approaches modeling the complex interactions between forest management and watershed services. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 100, 164-176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2018.12.007>
94. Paim, M.A., Salas, P., Lindner, S., Pollitt, H., Mercure, J.F., Edwards, N.R., Viñuales, J.E. (2020). Mainstreaming the Water-Energy-Food Nexus through Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs): The Case of Brazil. *Climate Policy*, 20, 163-78. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2019.1696736>.
95. Pereira, A. L., Johnson, E., Ferreira, P.J.S., de Santana Ribeiro, L.C., Carvalho, T.S., Pereira, H.B.B. (2019). Policy in Brazil (2016–2019) Threaten Conservation of the Amazon Rainforest. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 100, 8-12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2019.06.001>.
96. Pereira, A.L., Eder Johnson, Luiz Carlos de Santana Ribeiro, Lúcio Flávio da Silva Freitas, and Hernane Borges de Barros Pereira. 2020. ‘Brazilian Policy and Agribusiness Damage the Amazon Rainforest’. *Land Use Policy* 92 (March): 104491. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2020.104491>.
97. Peres, Carlos A., Toby A. Gardner, Jos Barlow, Jansen Zuanon, Fernanda Michalski, Alexander C. Lees, Ima C. G. Vieira, Fatima M. S. Moreira, and Kenneth J. Feeley. 2010. ‘Biodiversity Conservation in Human-Modified Amazonian Forest Landscapes’. *Biological Conservation*, Conserving complexity: Global change and community-scale interactions, 143 (10): 2314–27. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2010.01.021>.
98. Phillips, D. 2019. We are fighting’: Brazil’s indigenous groups unite to protect their land. <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2019/mar/04/we-are-fighting-brazils-indigenous-groups-unite-to-protect-their-land>
99. Potapov, Peter, Matthew C. Hansen, Lars Laestadius, Svetlana Turubanova, Alexey Yaroshenko, Christoph Thies, Wynet Smith, et al. 2017. ‘The Last Frontiers of Wilderness: Tracking Loss of Intact Forest Landscapes from 2000 to 2013’. *Science Advances* 3 (1): e1600821. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.1600821>.
100. Quijano, O. 2016. Ecosimías - Visiones y prácticas de diferencia económico/cultural en contextos de multiplicidad. Popayán: Editorial Universidad del Cauca https://www.academia.edu/31098275/Ecosimias_Visiones_y_pr%C3%A1cticas_de_diferencia_econ%C3%B3mico_cultural_en_contextos_de_multiplicidad_2a_edicion_2016_
101. RAISG - Red Amazónica de Información Socio Ambiental Geo-referenciada. 2020. Minería Ilegal. <https://mineria.amazoniasocioambiental.org/>

102. Reydon, B.P., Fernandes, V.B., Telles, T.S. (2020). Land Governance as a Precondition for Decreasing Deforestation in the Brazilian Amazon. *Land Use Policy*, 104313. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2019.104313>.
103. Ricco, M.E., and Whipps, J. 2016. 'Design Thinking Accelerated Leadership: Transforming Self, Transforming Community'. *The Journal of General Education* 65 (3–4): 159–77.
104. Ritter, C.D., McCrate, G., Nilsson, H., Fearnside, P.M., Palme, U., Antonelli, A. (2017). Environmental impact assessment in Brazilian Amazonia: Challenges and prospects to assess biodiversity. *Biological Conservation*, 206, 161-168. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2016.12.031>
105. RMIB-LAC The Indigenous Women's Biodiversity Network from Latin America and the Caribbean (Red de Mujeres Indígenas sobre Biodiversidad de America Latina y el Caribe. 2020. <https://localbiodiversityoutlooks.net/case-studies/the-indigenous-womens-biodiversity-network-from-latin-america-and-the-caribbean-rmib-lac/>
106. Rodríguez, C. 2010 *Sistemas agrícolas, chagras y seguridad alimentaria*. Bogotá: Fundación Tropenbos Internacional Colombia. Volumen 2. 58 p.
107. Ruiz-Mallén, I., and M. Heras. 2020. 'What Sustainability? Higher Education Institutions' Pathways to Reach the Agenda 2030 Goals'. *Sustainability (Switzerland)* 12 (4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12041290>.
108. Salick, J., Cellinese, N. and Knapp, S. 1997. Indigenous diversity of cassava: generation, maintenance use and loss among the Amuesha, Peruvian Upper Amazon. *Economic Botany*, 51(1): 6-19.
109. Santoro, Ninetta, Reid, Jo-Anne, Crawford, Laurie, and Simpson, Lee. 2012. 'Teaching Indigenous Teachers: Valuing Diverse Perspectives'. In *Social Inclusion and Higher Education*. Bristol University Press, Policy Press.
110. Santos Gómez, M. (2006). De la verticalidad a la horizontalidad. Reflexiones para una educación emancipadora. *Realidad: Revista de Ciencias Sociales y Humanidades*, 107, 39–64
111. Savarese, M. 2020. Brazil indigenous protest new gov't moves on their lands. <https://apnews.com/5557c508f532403b60239c1559aee6c7>
112. Scalise, M., Mendoza, M., Quiroz, I. (2020). Ethnobotanical Knowledge Encoded in Weenhayek Oral Tradition. *Journal of Ethnobiology*, 40, 39-55. <https://doi.org/10.2993/0278-0771-40.1.39>
113. Schüle W. 1992. Anthropogenic trigger effects on pleistocene climate? *Global Ecology and Biogeography Letters* 2: 33-36.
114. Schwandt, T., Ofir, Z., and D'Errico, S. 2016. 'Realising the SDGs by Reflecting on the Way(s) We Reason, Plan and Act: The Importance of Evaluative Thinking'. International Institute for Environment and Development.
115. SEEA EA (2017). *System of Environmental-Economic Accounting 2012- Applications and Extension*. Available on: https://seea.un.org/sites/seea.un.org/files/ae_final_en.pdf
116. Shackeroff, J.M., Campbell, L.M. (2007). Traditional Ecological Knowledge in Conservation Research: Problems and Prospects for their Constructive Engagement. *Conservation & Society*, 5, 343-360. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26392893>
117. Sheldrake, M. (2020). *Entangled life*. Available on: www.merlinsheldrake.com/entangled-life
118. Shepard, G. & H. Ramirez. 2011. "Made in Brazil": Human Dispersal of the Brazil Nut (*Bertholletia excelsa*, Lecythidaceae) in Ancient Amazonia. *Economic Botany* 65(1): 44-65.

119. SI – Survival International. 2020. Brazilian Indians. <https://www.survivalinternational.org/tribes/brazilian>
120. Silva Singh, Ananda, and Andréa Paula Segatto. 2020. 'When Relational Capabilities Walk in Education for Sustainability Scenario'. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 263 (August): 121478. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.121478>.
121. Spracklen, D.V., and L. Garcia-Carreras. 2015. 'The Impact of Amazonian Deforestation on Amazon Basin Rainfall'. *Geophysical Research Letters* 42 (21): 9546–52. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015GL066063>. Stolze Lima, T. S. 1996. O dois e seu múltiplo: reflexões sobre o perspectivismo em uma cosmologia Tupi. *Mana*. 2 (2):21-48.
122. Strathern, M. 1988 *Gender of the Gift*. Berkeley, CA: University of California Press. 98. Suess, E. 1875 *Die Entstehung der Alpen*. University of Michigan Library.
123. Tadaki, M., Sinner, J., and Šunde, C. 2020. 'Four Propositions about How Valuation Intervenes in Local Environmental Politics'. *People and Nature*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.10165>.
124. The Amazon Cooperation Treaty. (2019). ACTO and the Minamata Convention on Mercury. Available on: <http://www.otca-oficial.info/news/details/640> Access date: 4th Dec 2019
125. Towey, D., J. Walker, and R. Ng. 2019. 'Embracing Ambiguity: Agile Insights for Sustainability in Engineering in Traditional Higher Education and in Technical and Vocational Education and Training'. *Interactive Technology and Smart Education* 16 (2): 143–58. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ITSE-10-2018-0088>.
126. Tsavkko, R. 2020. Brazil's indigenous communities resist Bolsonaro. <https://www.dw.com/en/brazils-indigenous-communities-resist-bolsonaro/a-51909742>
127. Uexküll, J. 1937/2001. The new concept of Umwelt: A link between science and the humanities. *Semiotica* 134-1/4:111-123. De J. von Uexküll 1937 *Die neue Umweltlehre: Ein Bindeglied zwischen Natur-und Kulturwissenschaften*. *Die Erziehung* 13 (5): 185-199. Translated by Goësta Brunow.
128. Vatalis, K.I. 2017. 'Training Sustainability through Role Playing in Higher Education'. *Progress in Industrial Ecology* 11 (4): 361–72. <https://doi.org/10.1504/PIE.2017.092723>.
129. Villagómez, María Sol. 2018. "'Otras Pedagogías": La Experiencia de La Carrera de Educación Intercultural Bilingüe-UPS'. *Alteridad* 13 (1): 30–41. <https://doi.org/10.17163/alt.v13n1.2018.02>.
130. Viveiros de Castro, E. 1986 *Arawete: as deuses canibais*. Rio de Janeiro: J. Zahar/ANPOCS.
131. Viveiros de Castro, E. 2003. *Perspectivismo y Multinaturalismo en la América Indígena*. In A. Chaparro & C. Schumache *Racionalidad y Discurso Mítico*. Colombia: Centro Editorial Universidad del Rosario, ICAH. p. 191- 243.
132. Vleminckx, J., Schimann, H., Decaëns, T., Fichaux, M. et al. (2019). Coordinated community structure among trees, fungi and invertebrate groups in Amazonian rainforests. *Scientific reports - Nature research*, 9:11337 | <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-47595-6>
133. Wade, B., and T. Piccinini. 2020. 'Teaching Scenario Planning in Sustainability Courses: The Creative Play Method'. *Journal of Management Education* 44 (6): 699–725.
134. Walker, K. 2004. *Agricultural Change in the Bolivian Amazon* Center for Comparative Arch. University of Pittsburgh *Memoirs in Latin American Archaeology*, 13. 131 pp.
135. Walker, R. T., Simmons, C., Arima, E., Galvan-Miyoshi, Y., Antunes, A., Waylen, M., Irigaray, M. (2019). *Avoiding Amazonian Catastrophes: Prospects for Conservation in the 21st Century*. *One Earth*, 1, 202–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2019.09.009>

136. Walker, W. S., Gorelik, S. R., Baccin, A. (2020). The Role of Forest Conversion, Degradation, and Disturbance in the Carbon Dynamics of Amazon Indigenous Territories and Protected Areas. *PNAS*, <https://www.pnas.org/content/117/6/3015>.
137. Wamsler, Christine. 2020. 'Education for Sustainability: Fostering a More Conscious Society and Transformation towards Sustainability'. *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education* 21 (1): 112–30. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSHE-04-2019-0152>.
138. West, T., and Fearnside, P. 2021. 'Brazil's Conservation Reform and the Reduction of Deforestation in Amazonia'. *Land Use Policy* 100. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2020.105072>.
139. Wyness, L., and F. Dalton. 2018. 'The Value of Problem-Based Learning in Learning for Sustainability: Undergraduate Accounting Student Perspectives'. *Journal of Accounting Education* 45: 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaccedu.2018.09.001>.
140. Yu, K. (2021). Healing the world's cities. Talk - Frontiers Forum, 27th May 2021. Available on: Kongjian Yu | Nature-based solutions for ecological "sponge cities" - YouTube
141. Yu, W., Mullan, K., Biggs, T., Caviglia-Harris, J. et al. (2021). Do forests provide watershed services for farmers in the humid tropics? Evidence from the Brazilian Amazon. *Ecological Economics*, 183, 106965. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2021.106965>
142. Zafra-Calvo, N., Balvanera, P., Pascual, U., Merçon, J., Martín-López, B., van Noordwijk, M., et al. (2020). Plural valuation of nature for equity and sustainability: Insights from the Global South. *Global Environmental Change*, 63, 102115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2020.102115>
143. Zent, E. 2013 Jodí Ecogony, Venezuelan Amazon. *Environmental Research Letters* 8 (2013) 015008 <http://stacks.iop.org/1748-9326/8/015008>
144. Zent, E. 2014a Ecogonía II. Visiones alternativas de la biosfera en la América Indígena ¿Utopía o continuum de una noción vital? *Etnoecológica*. 10(7):1-21.
145. Zent, E. 2014b Ecogonía III. Jkyo jkwaini: la filosofía del cuidado de la vida de los joti del Amazonas venezolano. *Etnoecológica*. 10(8):1-28.
146. Zent, E. L. & S. Zent. Floristic Composition of Four Forest Plots: Sierra Maigualida, Venezuelan Guayana. *2004 Biodiversity and Conservation*. 13: 2453-2483.
147. Zidny, R., and I. Eilks. 2020. 'Integrating Perspectives from Indigenous Knowledge and Western Science in Secondary and Higher Chemistry Learning to Contribute to Sustainability Education'. *Sustainable Chemistry and Pharmacy* 16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scp.2020.100229>.